

IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN THE TRAVEL INDUSTRY

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Annotation. The tourism industry has been one of the fastest growing industries in the world economy in recent years, the rapid integration of digital transformation of all sectors of the global economy has had a special impact on the speed of industry development. The development of forms and trends in the tourism industry has stimulated the development of various types of tourism, and it has been at the forefront of digital technology and continues to be transformed around the world. The activation of this process has been triggered by the coronavirus pandemic. Also the development of digitalization was influenced by the restrictions on leaving home and visiting public institutions, the introduction of identity codes, due to which food delivery companies and other services became in demand, various digital solutions affecting the life of society as a whole, contributing and radical transformations in the tourism industry.

Keywords: tourism, digital transformation, technologies, artificial intelligence, competitiveness, information, development, service, information.

The rapid development of the digital economy in the world provides increasing competitiveness of countries, industries and enterprises. The ubiquitous level of digitalization entails significant changes in the process of business organization in tourism.

The main trend of the tourism industry at the present stage is the digital transformation, affecting all areas and focused on the global application of digital technology in the activities of tourism companies, as well as in the formation of an information, inclusive society and the digital economy as a whole¹.

The first digital services for tourists appeared in the early 2000s and were focused on online accommodation booking and ticket purchase. Booking.com - hotel aggregator gave potential customers the opportunity to see small hotels around the world. Airbnb - replicated the success of Booking.com by forming a new apartment rental market. Yandex Go, Uber, Gett - cab aggregators, attracted a huge number of people to small businesses, gave them the opportunity to earn money using their own car, and at the same time made cab services much more affordable.

Thus, the digital transformation of the tourism industry is the most urgent way out of the current crisis situation. Digital technologies, social networks and profiles, the Internet of Things, etc. will help boost tourism development and increase sales in this area. Despite the presence of certain barriers, the positive effect on the development of tourism is enormous, and the speed of overcoming the stated limitations, in turn, will be a key aspect for the formation of a new economic miracle "digital leap".

¹ Асаул В.В., Михайлова А.О. Обеспечение информационной безопасности в условиях формирования цифровой экономики // Теория и практика сервиса: экономика, социальная сфера, технологии. – 2018. – № 4 (38). – С. 5-9:

Our country is one of the countries with prospects for the development of tourism. The government of Uzbekistan continues to support the development of this industry in every way. Priority is given to the development of information, communication and digital technologies within the framework of the "2022-2026 Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan" aimed at implementing digital transformation in the country's national economy, industry and the entire society. In accordance with the directions of the strategy, it is planned to increase the number of local tourists to 12 million and the number of foreign tourists to 9 million within the framework of the "Travel Uzbekistan" program. Foreign investors are paying more attention to the tourism sector of Uzbekistan. Security, more than 9,000 places of pilgrimage, free tourist and economic zones and the improvement of the current legislation in the field of tourism have been noted by the foreign investment attraction agency as the investment advantages of the republic.

The main trend at the current stage of the tourism industry is the digital transformation, which affects all sectors and is aimed at the global application of digital technologies in the activities of tourism companies, as well as in the formation of information, inclusive society and digital economy.

The main distinguishing feature of the digital economy from the classical economy is the fact that the priority resources is the information, as well as methods of its management, which is an important factor for the tourism industry due to the fact that information in this area is the main element of production.

World Bank Group, 2018a	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the manifestation of qualitative and innovative changes consisting in individual digital transformations, and in digital changes in the structure of the economy, the use of data and digital technologies to create new activities or change existing ones.
OECD, 2019b	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> digital transformation is a set of economic and social effects resulting from the digitalization of a country.
ITU, 2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the use of innovative developments based on information and telecommunication technologies to solve various problems in tourism.
UNCTAD, 2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> directions for the radical impact of digital products and services on traditional sectors of the economy.
ITU, 2019a	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a continuous process of multimodal digitalization, changing the processes of creating, deploying and operating public and private sector services, making them personalized, paperless, cashless, and eliminating the physical presence, based on the consensus of the parties.
European Commission, 2019a	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> significant changes in all sectors of the economy and society as a result of the introduction of digital technology in all aspects of human life.

Figure 1. Definitions of digital transformation suggested by various international organizations²

Many researchers offer plenty of definitions of digital transformation. The evolution of digital technologies continues, and the content of this term evolves with them. And this is undoubtedly true, but, in our opinion, delineating the essence and content of the term "digital transformation" is not only an important task, but also extremely necessary at the current stage of digital economy development, allowing to form a common understanding, and, accordingly, to highlight the main directions of digital transformation³.

The main requirements for the implementation of digital platforms and the development of the ecosystem of platforms, which should be taken into account for the realization of these tools in the tourism industry, to which are the following: ⁴

1. Increasing the accuracy, of the data provided. Information in the digital economy is called the "new oil". The platform plays the role of a center of aggregation of quality data⁵, their processing and, consistent with the objectives of the platform participants, and their analysis.
2. Continuous statistical and dynamic ⁶research of the tourism market, institutionalization of relations between participants and clarity of their functioning. The results of the research are transformed into competences, models and rules.
3. Thorough elaboration of specialized information, in order to ensure the comprehensiveness and scalability of relationships within the industry.
4. Increasing the level of specialization of interactions between market participants, distribution of shares of responsibility within the platform;
5. Ensuring the security of data and transactions;
6. Freedom of choice and fair competition is an essential requirement for the effective functioning of the platform, allowing participants to combine and integrate their own or other digital solutions (e.g. booking.com and ozon travel ⁷integration) into the platform via API (application programming interface);
7. Standardization and regulation of the platform, which should dynamically and constructively adapt to market conditions and the external environment.

Conclusion. The prospects for the development of national tourism under the influence of digital transformation processes imply the development, first of all, of an international digital tourism space with the active use of qualitatively new labor; substantial state support,

² Author's research

³ Грибанов Юрий Иванович «Цифровая трансформация социально-экономических систем на основе развития института сервисной интеграции» Диссертация на соискание ученой степени доктора экономических наук Санкт-Петербург 2019

⁴ Lindroos N. The digital transformation of a ski resort: a case study. thesis, master of science. AALTO University School of science, 2017.

⁵ Агрегация данных — это процесс сбора всех ваших данных вместе. Многие организации собирают данные из нескольких источников с целью в конечном итоге объединить эти различные наборы данных. При агрегировании данных организации тщательно выбирают, откуда берутся их наборы данных, чтобы позже получить представление из сводной версии этих данных. Качество конечного анализа данных зависит от точности и тщательности агрегирования данных.

⁶ Динамическое исследование — это последовательный сбор отзывов от одной и той же группы людей в течение длительного периода времени. Динамическое исследование позволяет выполнить следующее: отслеживать изменения во мнениях и опыте людей своевременно выявлять проблемы, чтобы предотвратить негативные результаты

⁷ «Создание своего отдельного продукта, поддержка и интеграция с поставщиками – достаточно затратный процесс. Скорее всего, у Ozon.travel было недостаточно объемов, которые сделали бы это направление прибыльным. Сотрудничество с Booking.com позволит сервису дополнительно зарабатывать и при этом ничего не тратить.

including partial budget financing together with the attraction of private and foreign capital in the modernization of tourism infrastructure in the conditions of digital transformation; active application of robots and digital technologies for customer service, as well as with the use of new technologies for the development of international tourism. All these will give an additional impetus to the development of international tourism in the era of digitalization. Therefore, digitalization should be implemented for the benefit, not to the detriment, of international tourism development, and only in areas where it is rational.

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